

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF A POSITIVE ATTITUDE TO THE LESSON IN STUDENTS

Turgunova Gulnoza Mukhammadjonovna

Teacher at Namangan state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7997069>

Abstract. *In this article, the author highlights the socio-pedagogical support of the student's personality in the educational process - its importance in the development of personality, analyzing the abilities, interests, opportunities and conditions of children of different types, regularly studying the educational process aimed at the personality, as well as the favorable form and didactic possibilities of providing pedagogical assistance to the student.*

Keywords: *socio-pedagogical support, educational and educational approaches, positive attitude, psychological factor, cultural educational environment.*

In the modern continuous educational process, more than ever, it is necessary to pay attention to the problems of working with “difficult to learn”, “with complex characters”, “difficult teenager”, “prone to disorders”, “child with deviant behavior”, “dropout”.

Among student youth, among young people in general, the growth of “forgotten”, “difficult-to-bring”, delinquent, pedagogically deviant young men, of course, cannot but affect the educational process. After all, today's restless child tomorrow may grow up to be a potential criminal. That is why the conduct of educational activities with adolescents who have a negative attitude to school discipline requires a special approach.

As a result of our theoretical and practical research in general education schools in order to find answers to these questions, we can say that the level of professional skills and competence of many thousands of teachers currently working lags behind modern requirements. Based on the results of our scientific and methodological analyzes and the conclusions of the test, we think what should be paid attention to in order to improve the professional skills of a modern teacher and his competence (competences), to train competent, chubby and competitive staff.

First of all, it is very important to take into account the specifics of the changes taking place in our country, i.e. negative or positive impact of the national culture, mentality and way of life of the Uzbek people, as well as the transition period to a market economy, about education.

Secondly, education is of paramount importance in the formation of a person's personality and includes all the principles of the educational process.

Today's need for the priority of education requires how relevant the problem of organizing the educational process in shaping the student's personality is rationally and thoughtfully, covering all students equally.

Thirdly, based on the complexities associated with the transition to the market economy, it sets as an urgent problem the task of analyzing and studying the negative impact of some unpleasant situations occurring in our social life on the educational process, drawing certain scientific conclusions and developing methodological recommendations that can be applied in practice.

Fourthly, based on today's requirements, it is necessary to develop a concept that includes educational relations between school, family and neighborhood, takes into account national, religious, ethnic, territorial, demographic characteristics, and reveals a new content of education.

In general, the problems of education are related to the realization of the natural, social and political processes of a person by satisfying the spiritual development of a person, providing him with modern information, increasing the level of his interest in acquiring knowledge. After all, a skilled pedagogue can create conditions for the manifestation of both inner and outer abilities of each student and achieve his goal by looking for opportunities to further activate it.

It is important to take into account the specific features of the educational process when educating young people. Because the main figure in education is the teacher. No one can interfere with his imparting of knowledge, teaching methods, description of the subject, content of goals and tasks set for the lesson. In educational work, the opposite is true. There are various forces and factors that resist educational influences. In this sense, it is necessary to understand the difference between education and training. Because the main process that integrates the activity of the pedagogue and the student in the course of the lesson is education. At this point, it is necessary to consider the features of the educational process that are different from education.

Improving the educational process in our general secondary schools is directly related to increasing the educational power of education. The educational power of education is inextricably linked with the personality of the teacher, his professional ideological and moral qualities, organization, and perseverance. The quality of information provided to students cannot be improved without ensuring the integrity of the educational process. It is not for nothing that the teacher, who is the main organizer of the educational process, is considered to be the main driving force of the society. Therefore, if there is no balance between the teacher's words and practical activities, then the natural effect of education will gradually disappear.

Young people studying in the educational process of the continuous education system should learn from the teacher not only knowledge, but also universal human culture. In other words, it is a vital necessity that a person should be educated by a person. Unfortunately, the shallowness of universal human culture of most of our teachers involved in the educational process in our schools prevents us from achieving the intended result.

Communication between the teacher and the learner should be based on the spiritual needs, desires, wishes, mood, and intellectual capabilities of the learner. That is why the organizer of education should immediately find out the family conditions of each boy and girl taking lessons from him, the characteristics of family upbringing. For example, the social image of the hero of a newly published book in the family, or the relevance of a problem raised in such and such an article published in the daily media, with a child who grew up in a family, and the intellectual capabilities of a child who grew up in a family where books, newspapers, and magazines are the seed of the family, there is a big difference in the cultural level. Unfortunately, in the schools of the former Soviet regime, everyone was treated equally, without taking into account such sharp differences between students.

One of the most important criteria that determines the educational power of education is the tendency of young men and women who have completed the continuous education system and are entering an independent life, to work honestly and cleanly.

In addition to forming the qualities of hard work in students, it is necessary to establish a spirit of deep respect for the country's wealth and mother nature, self-examination, control, and

the ability to direct one's daily activities in the direction of correctness, goodness, justice, the interests of the country, and society. is one of the urgent tasks of the educational process.

Transferring the range of educational influence of education to the student's free time, increasing its effectiveness should be one of the most urgent problems of the continuous education system. In order to manage the educational process after the lesson, its manager must have high professional knowledge, experience and qualifications. Management of such a responsible and complex social mechanism cannot be left in the hands of people who cannot imagine the education system as a whole and do not know its structure.

There is also an invisible second side of the problem, what if the diploma specialist engaged in education did not have sufficient training and qualifications in higher pedagogical educational institutions? If they do not have the intellectual potential to educate a perfect person based on modern requirements, to ensure the continuous development of society, it is appropriate not to allow those who are only nominally “experts” to engage in the process of education.

REFERENCES

1. А.Авлоний. Туркий гулистон ёхуд ахлоқ. Т.-2000, 186 бет .
2. Андреева Г. М. Социальная психология: Учеб. для вузов. - М.: Аспект-Пресс, 2000. - 373 с.
3. Ўқувчиларда дарсга ижобий муносабатни шакллантиришга конструктив таъсир этиш технологиялари: - С.Т. Турғунов, Р.Мусурмонов, Ҳ. Тожибоева, Тошкент, 2016. -10 бет.
4. Подласый И.П. Курс лекций по коррекционной педагогике – М.:Владос – 2002- 332 с.
5. Рашидов Ҳ, Алимходжаева С. Дарс интизомига салбий муносабат: сабаблар таҳлили ва тавсиялар // Maktab va hayot. - Ташкент, 2014, - № 3 - 2-7 бетлар.
6. Рашидов Ҳ. Бошланғич синфларда дарсга муносабат муаммолари // “Бошланғич таълим сифати ва самарадорлигини ошириш: муаммолар ва ечимлар” мавзусидаги республика илмий-амалий конференция материаллари Тошкент, 2014 йил, 13 май. 143-145 бетлар.
7. <http://kutubxona.com/Баха-ад-Дин-Накшбанди-Афоризмы>
8. Sears R. Your ancients Resisted: A History of Child Psychology // E. N.Heterington (ed). Review of child development research. V. S. Chicago, 1975...." [Источник: <http://psychlib.ru/mgppu/ODE/ODE-001.htm>]